

Assessor View User Study

This questionnaire contains 4 sections (Sections 1, 3, 4, and 5 on LimeSurvey, Sections 2, and 6 as interviews on Zoom).

Section 1: Participant Information (In LimeSurvey)

1. Role and experience

- What is your designation? _____
- What is your primary role? _____
- How many years of experience do you have in this role? _____

2. Rate your knowledge on the following on a scale of Beginner to Expert.

Beginner Novice Intermediate Advanced Expert

Data visualization

Interpreting high-level diagrams
(e.g., privacy-related workflows)

GDPR

GDPR compliance

Data protection impact
assessment (DPIA)

Data privacy vocabulary (DPV)

Section 2: Current State-of-the-art (interview on Zoom)

1. Can you walk us through a privacy assessment process?

[IF YES] Can we talk to developers who have been a part of such a process?

[IF NO] If you don't have such a process, why not?

2. Who is involved in such an assessment? And who are the stakeholders?

3. Which parts of the assessment are manual? Which parts aren't, and how are they assisted?

4. What is your role in the assessment process?

[IF NO SPECIFIC ROLE] What kind of privacy-related work do you do?
Who are your clients?

5. Do privacy experts or legal experts have to understand source code to successfully complete such an assessment/ to advise your clients?

[IF YES] How do they navigate the process of understanding source code?

[IF NO] How do they decide if a software complies with GDPR?

6. Have you used any tools to verify whether a software complies with GDPR?

[IF YES] Which tools? Are they open-source? Are they user-friendly? Can you describe your workload?

[IF NO] Can you describe your workload?

7. Have you heard of DPV? Is DPV actively used in the assessment process?

Any plans of LTS version of DPV?

8. Which documents do data controllers need to complete to adhere to GDPR?

Records of processing activities (Art 30), DPIA document (Art 35), Privacy policy (Art 13)

Do you clients consult you to help complete these documents? Is this a manual process?

[IF NO] Which tools do you use? Are they open-source?

9. Are there any training programs specific to GDPR that are mandatory for the stakeholders involved in a privacy assessment process?

[IF YES] Do they cover automation i.e. do they introduce standardized tools?

Section 3: Evaluating a Privacy-Relevant Program Slice (In LimeSurvey)

You will use the Assessor View tool to examine a program slice.

1. The DPV specifications (model and diagram) provide a clear overview of the privacy practices in the program slice.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Explain your answer: _____

2. The DPV specifications help in identifying potential GDPR violations or areas requiring further investigation.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

If you strongly disagree/disagree, what improvements would you recommend?

3. The DPV specifications provide detailed insights into the specific data processing activities and flows.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Explain your answer: _____

Section 4: Understanding GDPR Compliance Warnings (In LimeSurvey)

You will use the Assessor View to examine whether the program slice complies with GDPR guidelines.

4. The warnings highlight potential GDPR compliance issues.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Please explain: _____

5. The warnings make it easier to assess GDPR principles such as data minimization, purpose limitation, or security measures.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Please explain: _____

6. The GDPR compliance warnings and suggestions are useful in guiding your analysis.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

What additional compliance-related insights would you like to see?

Section 5: Usability and Interactivity (In limesurvey)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

1. I would like to use Assessor view for my privacy-aware development needs.

2. I found Assessor view unnecessarily complex.

3. I found Assessor view easy to use.

4. I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use Assessor view.

5. I found the various functions in Assessor view to be well integrated.

6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in Assessor view.

7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use Assessor view very quickly.

8. I found Assessor view very cumbersome to use.

9. I felt confident using Assessor view.

10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with Assessor view.

How likely is it you would recommend Assessor view to a legal expert?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
(Not at all) (Go for it!)

Explain.

How likely is it you would recommend Assessor view to a privacy expert?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
(Not at all) (Go for it!)

Explain.

How likely is it you would recommend Assessor view to a DPO?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
(Not at all) (Go for it!)

Explain.

Section 6: Feedback and Recommendations (interview on Zoom)

4.1. What additional features or enhancements would you recommend for the DPV specifications? _____

4.2. Were there any missing aspects in the DPV specifications that you believe are critical for privacy assessment? _____

4.3. Do you think Assessor view reduces the reliance on developers or technical experts for privacy assessments?

- Yes / No

If yes, in what ways? _____

If no, what areas still require developer input? _____

4.4. Would you use the enhanced Assessor View in your own privacy assessment tasks?

- Yes / No

Please explain your answer: _____

4.5. Any additional feedback or suggestions: _____